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Trying to redefine defense policy in the European Union after the crisis in Ukraine

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Abstract: After the crisis in Ukraine, this work sought to give the impetus and definition of defense policy in the European Union (EU). The past is now behind us, as are the related problems. Defense as a European integration policy has followed a long path with many variables. Partnership, new EU Member States, the role of the NATO, respect for the UN Charter and the role of the EU bodies in the sector are some of the questionable points that lay the foundations for a new path that will arrive on its own path as a European “dream” by 2030. There are still many problems, the political will goes back and forth on what to follow for a common policy but we certainly need something new to face war crises inside our homes and above all to be ready for a future that the crises of war will not cease to exist as a reality of everyday life.

Keywords: European Defence; CSDP; CFSP; strategic compass; NATO; mutual assistance; Art. 42 TEU; financial support; EDA; inoperability.

The effects of the Ukrainian war on the CSDP

The continuous crises at the international level and especially after the war in Ukraine have pushed the EU to talk again and define the defense of the territory of the Union. The Russian armed attack was addressed through the Common Foreign and Security Policy (CFSP) and especially through military support for Ukraine and restrictive measures against Russia and its Belarusian ally. The EU has exercised its actions through the competences of the Treaty of Lisbon and above all to address the migratory crisis, the temporary protection of displaced persons and the economic effects of the conflict on the European market¹.

The war behind the “European house” had the effect in March of 2022 of the adoption of the Strategic Compass², a document of a programmatic nature which made autonomy the strategic level to set objectives for the development of the Common Security and Defense Policy (CSDP) within the distant 2030. The uncertainty of continuous wars (Pedersen, 2006)³, and on the

¹Council Regulation (EU) 2022/2578 of 22 December 2022 establishing a market correction mechanism to protect citizens of the Union and the economy from excessively high prices, in OJ EU L 335/2022, 45.

²A Strategic Compass for Security and Defense-For a European Union that protects its citizens, its values and its interests and contributes to international peace and security, Brussels, 21 March 2022, 7371/22.

³Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Denmark, Danes vote yes to abolish EU defence opt-out – here are the next steps, 2 June 2022: “(...) we can now fully participate in the European cooperation on security and defence. And we can thereby take greater responsibility for security in our own neighbourhood. This is a good and important step. Unity in Europe is the best answer we can give in the current situation (...)”.

other hand Denmark which dissolved the opting-out that came from the distant Maastricht Treaty of 1992⁴ allowed EU's involvement in military and defense issues for about thirty years. Already since 1 July 2022 Denmark has been bound by the CSDP⁵ and has started to contribute at a military level (Jakobsen, 2009; Genschel, Jachtenfuchs, Migliorati, 2023) and since 23 March 2023 it has decided to be part of the European Defense Agency (EDA)⁶ and even after two months to also be part of the Permanent Structured Cooperation (PESCO). Some EU Member States have also asked NATO to join, which after a troubled negotiation joined together with Sweden.

We can speak for an integration beyond the CSDP given the partnership through NATO and EU since 24 February 2022 which has led organizations to adopt documents of a programmatic nature, thus demonstrating the guarantee for European defence.

These institutional developments were capable of orienting European integration towards a narrower, more homogeneous and continuous development path in the defense sector, a progress which has followed slow and difficult steps in recent years. European defense has always been approached at least in

⁴The acts relating to Denmark and the relevant annex, in GUCE C 348/1992, 1.

⁵See Art. 26, par. 1 and 42, 43, 46 TEU.

⁶European Defense Agency, Denmark joins the European Defense Agency, 23 March 2023. Council Decision (CFSP) 2023/1015 of 23 May 2023 confirming Denmark's participation in PESCO and amending Decision (CFSP) 2017/2315, establishing permanent structured cooperation (PESCO) and establishes the list of participating Member States, in OJEU L 136/2023, 73ss.

theory as an autonomous strategy following Art. 42, par. 2 TEU (Leino-Sandberg, Ojanen, 2022). Within this context we can notice also Art. 24, par. 1 TEU (Blanke, Mangiamelli, 2021) where its prerogatives do not follow the common objectives of all Member States.

With the Treaty of Lisbon, the ESDP was renamed to CSDP as a discipline that enriched and emancipated the regulatory profile that dates back to the genesis of the EU. The CSDP was introduced in Title V TEU, Chapter 2 relating to the provisions on the common security and defense policy (Articles 42 to 46 TEU) and the ad hoc regulations (Blanke, Mangiamelli, 2021). The contents of the ESDP in light of the creation of the EDA introduce innovations to stimulate integration between Member States in the defense sector. This identifies the relative competence in security, evolution, implementation of interventions with peacekeeping missions, crisis scenarios and the development of the military capabilities of the EU to protect the territory of the EU. These are distinct, complementary components that can be influenced by the development of a European security and defense component. Military peacekeeping missions bring important elements of information on armaments and logistics for defense development and cooperation. The defense component is useful for carrying out peacekeeping missions as well as for integration in the sector in

the Member States and within the context of different speeds. The security component has also had strong impulses of a regulatory nature towards the integration of defense as an important policy to reach PESCO. But are security and defense the same thing? Do they mix with each other? What problems do they present?

Practice through the “safety” component

When we talk about the security component we are referring to the objectives of military orientations and the creation of structures that are dedicated to civilian capabilities. This is a *modus procedendi* that has continued for years and achieves the objectives of the CSDP. In this spirit, we also remember in PESCO the decision of the European Council of 22 and 23 June 2017 and the setting of the objectives that drive the acceleration of the implementation of projects concerning infrastructure and military mobility as they are organized by the European Council of 15 December 2022.

The security component was based on Article 42, par. 1 TEU (Blanke, Mangiamelli, 2021) which takes into consideration the civil and military operational capabilities that have been provided by the Member States and the conduct of peacekeeping missions and the implementation of the principles of the UN Charter. Past practice tells us of a discreet and variable

participation on the part of the EU Member States which depends on the type of peacekeeping mission to initiate the necessary capabilities and carried out in the Treaty of Lisbon according to Art. 42, par. 5 TEU and Art. 44 TEU where the Council has entrusted the related peacekeeping and the group of Member States that wish to do so and that can provide the relevant necessary capabilities. The Council has not made decisions that are based on primary provisions but on new developments that arise from the strategic compass. Thus it is a practice that is implemented according to the ex Art. 17 TEU. Art. 43 TEU (Blanke, Mangiamelli, 2021) specifies that the missions of combat units for the management of every crisis within the European context or not tends towards the re-establishment of peace and conflict operations arriving at the contribution to the fight against international terrorism.

As regards peacekeeping missions in the territory of one or more third states, they are part of the security component which is understood externally and refers to the maintenance of peace and security in the international community and with particular regard to crisis scenarios found in the European context. When cases of terrorism are noticed Art. 43 TEU organizes related peacekeeping missions that contribute to the fight against criminal conduct through the support of third states. Terrorist threats affecting the interior of the EU by dedicating itself to the

rules that have to do with the area of freedom, security and justice and the solidarity clause provided for by Art. 222 TFEU (Blanke, Mangiamelli, 2021).

On some interventions⁷ the “security component” began its journey in 2003 and above all after the civil police mission in Bosnia-Herzegovina⁸. An intervention which in the practice of peacekeeping missions has around twenty-six civil and fifteen military interventions which are carried out in the conduction phase. The military interventions included a deployment of the armed forces of the participating countries and third states with the objective of maintaining and building peace (Blockmans, Spornbauer, 2013). Civilian missions, on the other hand, are created by unarmed intervention groups, but include the relative deployment of police, customs and technical forces, thus supporting local authorities in maintaining internal order and promoting the rule of law⁹.

These are peace missions that are part of a crisis scenario that brings together and supports the evolution of the local situation as well as reinvigorating the interventions in the place that are implemented¹⁰. The related interventions also concern

⁷See the Council Joint Action of 22 December 2000 on the European Union Monitoring Mission (2000/811/CFSP), in OJEU L 328/2000, 53ss.

⁸the Council Joint Action of 11 March 2002 on the European Union Police Mission (2002/210/CFSP), in OJEU L 70/2002, 1ss, et seq. mod.

⁹Council Joint Action 2004/570/CFSP of 12 July 2004 relating to the European Union military operation in Bosnia-Herzegovina, in OJEU L 252/2004, 10ss.

¹⁰Council Decision 2013/354/CFSP of 3 July 2013 on the European Union Police Mission for the Palestinian Territories, in OJEU L 185/2013, 12ss. Council Joint Action 2005/776/CFSP of 7 November 2005 amending the mandate of the European

neighboring states that need civil and military support that undermine and threaten the external security of the EU. In particular, third states concern the case of the former Yugoslavia where peace missions represent stabilization tools that are useful for the rapprochement and accession of the EU itself. Thus we read that peacekeeping missions have also started in Ukraine. Missions of a package of measures supporting a third state where the EUNAM military assistance which was started at the end of 2022 had as its task to create Ukrainian armed forces and enable the defense and territorial integrity of their country within the borders they recognize internationally¹¹.

Within this level of crisis we recall the cases of peacekeeping missions in Africa which undermine external security given that the variety of peacekeeping missions are initiated and which testify to the needs of third states that are interested in such support. Even in Asia the EU has sent peacekeeping missions,

Union Special Representative for Moldova, in OJEU L 292/2005, 113ss. Council Joint Action 2004/523/CFSP of 28 June 2004 relating to the European Union rule of law mission in Georgia, in OJEU L 228/2004, 21ss. See Council Joint Action 2008/851/CFSP of 10 November 2008 on the European Union military operation to contribute to the deterrence, prevention and suppression of acts of piracy and armed robbery in off the coast of Somalia, in OJEU L 301/2008, 33ss, et seq. mod. Council Decision 2010/96/CFSP of 15 February 2010 relating to the European Union military mission to contribute to the training of the Somali security forces, in OJEU L 44/2010, 16ss. Council Decision 2012/389/CFSP of 16 July 2012 on the European Union Mission for the Development of Regional Maritime Capabilities in the Horn of Africa (EUCAP NESTOR), in OJEU L 187/2012, 40ss.

¹¹Council Decision (CFSP) 2022/1968 of 17 October 2022 on a European Union military assistance mission in support of Ukraine (EUMAM Ukraine), in OJEU L 270/2022, 85ss.

especially in the Palestinian territories¹², in Iraq after Saddam's period of hegemony¹³, in Afghanistan¹⁴ and in Indonesia¹⁵.

The security component is thus seen as inclusive and common to several third states that participate in peacekeeping missions in the EU as well as in individual interventions in a systematic way. The evolving legal instrument guarantees the external participation of the international agreement stipulated according to Art. 37 TEU. The practice dates back to Art. 24 TEU and is referring to the types of international agreements¹⁶. The EU has stipulated within this framework various precise international agreements with third states for participation in individual peacekeeping missions which were called participation agreements. The EU has concluded more than twenty international agreements with third states that have accommodated peacekeeping missions by establishing general rules of participation as agreements on a participation

¹²Council Decision 2013/354/CFSP of 3 July 2013 on the European Union Police Mission for the Palestinian Territories (EUPOL COPPS) OJ L 185, 4.7.2013, p. 12-15.

¹³Council Decision (CFSP) 2017/1869 of 16 October 2017 on the European Union Advisory Mission in support of security sector reform in Iraq, in OJEU L 266/2017, 12ss.

¹⁴Council Decision 2010/279/CFSP of 18 May 2010 on the European Union Police Mission in Afghanistan, in OJEU L 123/2010, 4ss.

¹⁵Council Joint Action 2005/643/CFSP of 9 September 2005 on the European Union Monitoring Mission in Aceh, in OJEU L 234/2005, 13ss.

¹⁶Peacekeeping missions also involve the stipulation between the EU and the territorial sovereign of a relevant agreement to authorize entry and legal status, the so-called status-of-mission-agreement or status-of-forces-agreement depending on the civil nature and military of the intervention.

framework¹⁷. This inclusive spirit has included cooperation with international organizations where the EU has initiated the relevant partnership to formalize soft law acts that are integrated into international agreements according to specific aspects¹⁸. This is a rich practice through partnerships where the EU alongside the UN, NATO and the African Union and the Association of South-East Asian Nations (ASEAN) bring elements of discussion and evaluation.

The “defense” component

The defense component projected through ex Art. 17 TEU and from a gradual definition of a common defense policy which led to a common defense where the European Council decided unanimously, reaching up to PESCO¹⁹. The mutual defense assistance clause inspired by the former Art. 42, par. 7 TEU (Blanke, Mangiamelli, 2021).

¹⁷These are third states for the near future such as: Iceland, Norway, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Montenegro, Serbia, the Republic of Macedonia, Albania, Moldova, Ukraine, Turkey and Georgia, South Korea, Australia, New Zealand, the United States, Canada, Colombia and Chile.

¹⁸Council Decision 2003/211/CFSP of 24 February 2003 on the conclusion of an Agreement between the European Union and the North Atlantic Treaty Organization on Security of Information, in OJEU L 80/2003, 35, and Council Decision (CFSP) 2020/1726 of 14 September 2020 on the signature and conclusion, on behalf of the Union, of the Framework Agreement between the European Union and the United Nations on the provision of mutual support in the framework of respective missions and field operations, in OJEU L 389/2020, 1.

¹⁹Art. 42, par. 6, and art. 46 TUE.

The defense component has achieved a slow path for certainly political, strategic and identity reasons, thus constituting a brake on the evolution and European integration in the sector. On the other hand, the aspects of identity, the neutrality of other states and the non-collaboration with the armed forces have shown a slow evolution of the defense component and an explanation for a European context where defensive alliances and in particular the role of NATO has played an important role towards solid and active defensive mechanisms especially after the fall of Berlin. Thus NATO appeared as an alternative to European defense integration. An evolution of a defense component to a defense apparatus alongside the Western European Union (WEU) where until 2011 the difficulty and above all the lack of will of the EU Member States to assume the related financial commitments of support and compliance with those imposed were slowed down to belonging to defensive alliances.

What are the relations with NATO?

Since the Maastricht Treaty, NATO was a leitmotif of the CSDP which has remained reproduced on various occasions also through the treaties as seen in Art. 42, par. 2 TEU. Its development was advanced and progressed through the membership of several Member States and organizations that followed international obligations as a relationship that was

understood in terms of interference of a mutual nature while avoiding duplication of costs and discrimination between EU Member States, NATO and the states that are only part of the Atlantic alliance²⁰.

As an important launch between NATO and EU the Berlin plus of 16 December 2002 with the organization of the peacekeeping missions of the EU. This is an agreement that formalized, perhaps for the first time, the provisions of the Union, military and logistical resources, requiring a commitment to implementation on site. A cooperation that has allowed for forms of rapprochement and coordination between two organizations in different theaters of operation in the Balkans²¹, such as cooperation that concerns the security of the CFSP and the defense component. This “marriage” after the Treaty of Lisbon led the organizations to update the contents of the Berlin plus agreement and the priorities created and designed

20M.K. Albright, The Right Balance Will Secure NATO's Future, in *Financial Times*, 7 December 1998: “(...) the key is to make sure that any institutional change is consistent with basic principles that have served the Atlantic partnership well for 50 years. This means avoiding what I would call the Three Ds: decoupling, duplication, and discrimination. First, we want to avoid decoupling: Nato is the expression of the indispensable transatlantic link. It should remain an organisation of sovereign allies, where European decision-making is not unhooked from broader alliance decision-making. Second, we want to avoid duplication: defence resources are too scarce for allies to conduct force planning, operate command structures, and make procurement decisions twice-once at Nato and once more at the EU. And third, we want to avoid any discrimination against Nato members who are not EU members (...)”.

21Joint Action 2003/92/CFSP of 27 January 2003 relating to the European Union military operation in the former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia, in OJEU L 34/2003, 26ss. Council Joint Action 2004/570/CFSP of 12 July 2004 relating to the European Union military operation in Bosnia and Herzegovina, in OJEU L 252/2004, 10ss.

(Blockmans, 2019) arriving in time at an EU-NATO cooperation of 10 January 2023 which established that the strategic compass with the NATO strategic concept of 2022 have developed the partnership of complementarity and interoperability, thus effectively addressing the aggression that is registered in the international community.

The declaration of 2023 recognized the value of European defense as “stronger and more capable” and placed NATO as a necessary organization between two organizations that act in a coordinated and synergistic way given that NATO's defensive role has not been questioned (Herold, Schmitt, Sloan, 2022)²².

The points of contact between NATO and EU in the defense sector are in line with the common desire to act in a complementary and interoperable way and without attacking the role played by the alliance in the European context. The development of the two organizations and especially after the accession of Denmark, Sweden and Finland have paved the way for a path more similar and in keeping international peace and stability. The memberships of the two organizations do not coincide and the participation in NATO of non-European states²³

22“(…) NATO and the EU play complementary, coherent and mutually reinforcing roles in supporting international peace and security (...) NATO recognises the value of a stronger and more capable European defence that contributes positively to transatlantic and global security and is complementary to, and interoperable with NATO. Initiatives to increase defence spending and develop coherent, mutually reinforcing capabilities, while avoiding unnecessary duplications, are key to our joint efforts to make the Euro-Atlantic area safe (...)”.

23Art. 49 TEU.

makes complementarity necessary between two entities that are not similar but with objectives in common of an alliance that benefits from the double solidarity since 2023:

“(…) allies within the NATO which are not members of the EU to participate as much as possible in the latter's initiatives (...) (as well as) EU Member States which are not part of the Alliance to participate as much as possible in NATO's initiatives (...) anticipate that the reference to “non-EU” allies found expression in the participation of some third states in PESCO (...). PESCO projects were started within NATO and subsequently passed into the CSDP. These are cases in which the arrival of the projects at the CSDP was anticipated by the necessary management and financial assessments (for example, possible financial support from the EU) and also accompanied by the guarantee, offered by the states involved, that the implementation would continue at a European level (...)”.

The harmonized integration path within the CSDP. The case of the European Defense Agency

It is obvious that the EDA was an important stage in the creation of an important path of European defense. An agency that was established by the Joint Action 2004/551/CFSP²⁴ with the objective:

“(…) to assist the Council and the Member States in the effort to improve the EU's defense capabilities in the field of crisis management and to support the ESDP in its current and future structure without prejudice to national competences, the agency soon also became the headquarters for the management of defense projects and programs, as well as research activities in synergy with the military sector industry (...)”.

The tasks of the EDA are the identification and contribution of operational needs, the promotion of measures to respond and contribute, identify any useful measure to an industrial, technological defense base to participate in the definition of a

²⁴Council Joint Action 2004/551/CFSP of 12 July 2004 on the creation of the European Defense Agency, in OJEU L 245/2004, 17ss.

European armaments policy and to Council assistance in assessing military capabilities. According to Art. 45, par. 1 TEU indicates the tasks that seem to group into some categories the achievement of objectives concerning the development of the military missions of the EU and the promotion of cooperation between Member States in the armaments sector.

According to Art. 45, par. 2 TEU, the Council adopted by qualified majority a decision in the CFSP context which concerned the statute, headquarters and operating methods of the EDA adopted in Decision 2011/411 and subsequently repealed and recast in Decision 2015/1835²⁵. Changes that have expanded tasks assigned to the agency in developments that have occurred within the CSDP and with regard to PESCO.

Within this context, we recall the Coordinated Annual Review On Defense (CARD procedure) which was initiated by the Foreign Affairs Council of 18 May 2017 for the creation of an implementation plan on security and defense in 2016. The procedure encouraged the related integration harmonization of Member States by strengthening the national military capabilities of the EU. The CARD procedure relating to the period 2021-2022 influenced the outbreak of the war in Ukraine and sought to fill investment gaps thus noting past monitoring.

²⁵Council Decision 2011/411/CFSP of 12 July 2011 establishing the statute, seat and operating rules of the European Defense Agency and repealing Joint Action 2004/551/CFSP, in OJEU L 183/2011, 16ss. Decision (CFSP) 2015/1835 (recast), in OJEU L 266/2015, 55ss.

The Defense Spending Recommendations monitored and organized the defense spending sector of 2022. The agency sought to increase military spending and reduce financial fragmentation by exceeding projects that are joint in capacity development. Member States are invited to indicate the steps that have followed the investment parameters by 2025 as pre-established by PESCO. The agency has sought to harmonize data and information on military spending, facilitating investment priorities through analysis and improving opportunities for cooperation between Member States²⁶. According to Art. 45, par. 2 TEU the agency allowed the participation, even voluntary, of activities that by 2023 the Member States adhering to the CSDP were part of the agency, thus showing the way to a differentiated integration tool.

The agency is now an organ of the EU and as an integration tool of the CSDP where it exclusively implements the security component of PESCO and from an external point of view it allows third parties to stipulate administrative agreements and to join its activities especially on the condition of military projects.

Permanent structured cooperation

PESCO is now a harmonization and integration body in the

²⁶European Defence Agency, 2022 Coordinated Annual Review on Defence Report, November 2022.

defense sector and voluntary participation has required participating Member States to commit and invest in military development and capabilities. This is a legal framework of a binding nature where the commitments undertaken at the time of joining PESCO have as their objective the binding of the participating Member States. According to Articles 42, par. 6 and 46 TEU and Decision 2017/2315²⁷ where the Council created PESCO with twenty-three members and the recent membership of Denmark with Decision 2023/1015 has arrived at a number of participants which despite the non-participation of Malta continues to maintain a form of differentiated integration between Member States which still calls into question various points of a political nature. In particular, Maltese Prime Minister Muscat states that:

“(…) Malta will adopt a wait and see attitude to understand how PESCO evolves and determine whether it contradicts the country's neutrality (….) he had also said that he did not foresee any particular neutrality-related issue (Sansone, 2023) (….) while maintaining Malta's sovereignty to decide whether or not to join PESCO, it seems to us that the position taken presents some inconsistencies. On the one hand, it is consistent with the Maltese state's non-belonging to NATO (of which, however, it is a partner) or to other defensive alliances (….) the opting-out from PESCO does not seem in line with Malta's participation in the CSDP and its implementation, with the accession to the EDA and the increase in military spending decided on the recommendation of the agency, and also with the adoption of the European Peace Facility. The implementation of which through the provision of financial resources intended for the acquisition of military equipment is difficult to reconcile, at first sight, with the status of neutrality (….) the constraint imposed by Art. 42, par. 7, TEU, is inconsistent with neutrality which if activated following an

²⁷Council Decision (CFSP) 2017/2315 of 11 December 2017 establishing permanent structured cooperation (PESCO) and establishing the list of participating Member States, in OJEU L 331/2017, 57ss.

armed aggression against another EU Member State, would require Malta to make its armed forces and logistics available, in terms entirely similar to those that characterize the functioning of the defensive alliances (...) by virtue of the same clause, in the event of armed aggression on its territory. Malta could count on the direct help of the other EU Member States (...).²⁸ The inception of PESCO adopted decisions relating to new projects²⁸, rules for governance²⁹, conditions allowing the participation and invitation of third states³⁰ as well as according to Art. 46, par. 3 TEU the participation of Denmark.

PESCO has as its main objective participation in activities that are conducted within its scope and which include participating Member States with the exception of Malta. PESCO is open to third states that want to participate within their sphere in conduct projects³¹ which lead to a number that exceeds seventy in various sectors such as training and facilities, land, maritime, air, resource sharing, cyber and command, control and space³²

²⁸Council Decision (CFSP) 2018/340 of 6 March 2018, which establishes the list of projects to be developed within PESCO, in OJEU L 65/2018, 24ss, amended several times, most recently by the Decision (CFSP) 2023/995 of the Council of 22 May 2023 amending and updating Decision (CFSP) 2018/340, which establishes the list of projects to be developed within PESCO, in OJEU L 135/2023, 123ss.

²⁹Council Decision (CFSP) 2018/909 of 25 June 2018 establishing a set of governance rules for PESCO projects, in OJEU L 161/2018, 37ss.

³⁰Council Decision (CFSP) 2020/1639 of 5 November 2020 establishing the general conditions under which third States may exceptionally be invited to participate in individual PESCO projects, in OJEU L 371/2020, 3ss.

³¹Council Decision (CFSP) 2021/748 of 6 May 2021 on the participation of Canada in the PESCO Military Mobility project and similar decisions concerning Norway (CFSP Decision 2021/749) and for the United States (CFSP Decision 2021/750), all in OJEU L 160/2021, 106ss. Decision (CFSP) 2022/2244 relating to the participation of the United Kingdom, in OJEU L 294/2022, 22ss. Council Decision (CFSP) 2023/385 of 20 February 2023 on the participation of Canada in the PESCO project Network of logistics centers in Europe and support for operations, in OJEU L 53/2023, 14ss.

³²Please note that four of these projects are already closed. These are co-basing, EU Test and Evaluation Centers (EUTEC), European Union Training Mission Competence Center (EU TMCC) and Indirect Fire Support Capability (EuroArtillery).

where PESCO participating Member States join on a voluntary basis. Projects that implement groups of Member States that range from approximately twenty-five participants and in cases that are supported by third states.

PESCO also means military mobility which takes all other Member States as participants. We remember the case of Norway, Canada, United States and United Kingdom as well as Switzerland which is about to join (Pugnet, 2023). It is a participation that explains some factors. The military mobility started within NATO and subsequently passed through PESCO and the CSDP as a project that supports a significant number of states that are starting to continue the implementation of financial support from the EU thanks to the European Defense Fund and the Connecting Mechanism Europe 2012-2027. Joining the project leads to a high strategic level and proposes a simplification of standards to speed up national cross-border military transport procedures by road, sea, air and rail. This strategy has an important relevance for Ukraine's armaments and legitimate defense which requires a rapid, possible movement of means within the military Schengen³³.

Thus the implementation of PESCO plays a gradual, important role in common defense policy. Already the European Defense

³³See the Recommendation of 14 November 2022 assessing the progress made by the participating Member States towards the implementation of the commitments undertaken in the framework of permanent structured cooperation, 2022/C 433/02, in OJEU C 433/2022, 6ss), the Council meeting of 29 and 30 June 2023 expressed satisfaction with the state of progress of the work (see conclusions, par. 28).

Reflection Paper of 2017³⁴ through the Commission sought to contribute to a debate on the role of the EU in matters of security, defense and the related access debate for the post-Brexit period. Within this context, some cooperation scenarios are proposed that will be concrete by 2025. Scenarios where member states:

“(...) (a) continue voluntary and non-binding cooperation in defense matters, (b) reach a policy of shared defense, in which greater cooperation is the norm rather than the exception and, finally, (c) they cooperate and integrate to the point of developing a common defense (...). The CSDP cooperation occurred voluntarily, as in scenario (a), at least until the launch of PESCO, which made collaboration between member states more binding (...). The common defense policy can correspond to scenario (b) and the cooperative methods envisaged by it, to which we will return, and that the common defense responds to scenario (c) (...). PESCO can be placed between scenarios (a) and (b), since, as a highly inclusive binding legal framework which has reached the operational phase, it seems to us overcome the mere voluntary cooperation referred to in scenario (a), to tend towards integration “as a rule” which characterizes scenario (b), reasonably corresponding to the common defense policy (...) appears to us to be operationally projected towards the definition of a common defense policy. Once achieved it will be possible to look towards the further objective of creating a common defense (c) (...)”.

Mutual defensive assistance

Par. 7 of Art. 42 TEU (Virkkunen, 2022; Mickonytė, 2022) provided that in the case of an armed attack on the territory of a Member State. Member States can help and assist with all the relevant means at their disposal and as established by Art. 51 of the UN Charter the relevant individual and collective self-defense. A mutual defensive assistance that brings similarities and differences in content according to Art. 5 of the Atlantic

³⁴COM(2017) 315 final, Bruxelles, 7 June 2017.

Pact. A point in common is that the two rules take into consideration the activation of collective defence. Art. 5 calls an armed attack against an ally and Art. 42, par. 7 TEU refers to an armed attack on the territory of a Member State. The difference between an armed attack and armed aggression seems to be blurred. The UN Charter and aggression refers to art. 39 as the basis of the legitimacy of the Security Council of the UN and the related powers of Chapter VII of the UN Charter. While the notion of an armed attack is contained in art. 51, as a fact that authorizes the exercise of the natural right to self-defense in an individual and/or collective manner, also including conduct that presupposes the use of armed force³⁵.

The use of armed force, violation of international borders, armed reprisals, military occupation, forcible annexation of foreign territories, bombings against other states even indirectly, support for irregular forces or armed gangs in carrying out hostile acts and military are arguments that place aggression and armed attack into a specific relationship and the activation of different clauses. Clauses based on Art. 42, par. 7 TEU and Art. 5 of the Atlantic Pact which exists in substantial divergences. Distinction between concepts that detect defensive assistance clauses and reference is made to the same hypotheses that concern the use of

³⁵See the Resolution 2625 (XXV) of the General Assembly on friendly relations between States of 24 October 1970, the resolution of the General Assembly on the definition of aggression of 14 December 1974, as well as the ruling of the International Court of Justice in the case of military and paramilitary activities in and against Nicaragua (Nicaragua vs. United States) on 27 June 1986.

force on a territory of an alliance and on the sovereignty of an EU Member State³⁶ requirements that are part of an aggression classified as type of armed assault.

Art. 42, par. 7 TEU with peremptory manner towards Art. 5 of the Atlantic Pact seems to give the allies discretion to face an armed attack against one of them. This is an application practice that is compliant according to Art. 5 an appreciation of the terms of this type of discretion. In particular, the Przewodów episode showed us that Art. 5 led to a rapid reaction. On 15 November 2022 missiles fell on Polish territory and killed two people and in the previous hours ascertained the mistake that was made in the Kiev air attack and in institutional environments where the hypothesis of a NATO reaction against Russia had opened the way to call Poland the Atlantic Council for the discussion and related evaluation of what happened.

Art. 51 of the UN Charter records a substantial identity which is contained between Art. 42, par. 7 TEU and Art. 5 of the Atlantic Pact with the difference that the second lies in a reproduction of the Atlantic norm and the provision of the UN which is related to the powers of the UN Security Council³⁷.

³⁶Deen, B., Zandee, D., Stoetman, A. (2022, January, 7). Uncharted and uncomfortable in European defence. The EU's mutual assistance clause of Article 42(7). Netherlands Institute of International Relations.

³⁷The treaty norm for self-defense reports that: "(...) the Security Council has not taken the measures necessary to maintain international peace and security (...) immediately brought to the attention of the Security Council (...) undertake at any time such action as it deems necessary to maintain or re-establish international peace and security (...)".

Does the matter remain open when a Member State of the UN and NATO suffers hostile action of an armed nature if the two clauses remain active? We must say that from a formal point of view Art. 42, par. 7 TEU and Art. 5 of the Atlantic Pact can be activated in the face of hostile and armed conduct, contributing to the defense of one's territory. The two clauses do not reach the same basis of operation. According to the strategic compass of 2022 it is envisaged that the exercises that are joint between the armed forces and the EU Member States will put into operation Art. 42, par. 7 TEU where Art. 5 of the Atlantic Pact continues to be in action. The two clauses are equally operative and the issue in the contextual case coordinates the conduct of the defense in the field. This eventuality leads to a possible development despite the fact that the exercises according to Art. 42, par. 7 TEU are successfully held and that only critical conduct exercises guarantee mutual defensive assistance within the EU in an active and effective manner.

The operation of Art. 5 of the Atlantic Pact also takes positions that are different from Art. 42, par. 7 TEU and which does not include the maximum possible satisfaction from a logistical, technical point of view³⁸. Some states such as Poland and the Baltic states were afraid that Art. 42, par. 7 TEU effectively replaces the guarantee offered by Art. 5 of the Atlantic Pact.

³⁸Clapp, S. (2022, December). Implementation of the Strategic Compass. Opportunities, challenges and timelines, European Parliament Research Service, 18ss.

Austria, Ireland as neutral Member States put Art. 42, par. 7 TEU to counteract their status and as it was stated that “would invoke their neutrality should a decisive moment arise”.

Another group that includes Germany is oriented towards the logic that Art. 42, par. 7 TEU is operational without any need to rely on questions of an interpretative nature. Member States operate according to Art. 42, par. 7 TEU where they also include Greece and Cyprus which consider mutual defensive assistance as a type of European guarantee in the face of Turkey's aggression and covered under Art. 5 of the Atlantic Pact. Sweden and Finland became members of NATO arguing that the mutual defense assistance clause is an important step for their European integration in the defense sector and in finis France which without reservations strengthens the mutual defense assistance clause according to Art. 5 of the Atlantic Pact. In short, each Member State, according to its own political needs, has taken positions which in finis are similar to the protection of a common defense in the European context for a greater establishment of peace and security in the Balkans and beyond.

In finis, we can say that the partnership bond between NATO and the EU guarantees a form of protection, expressing the hope that in the near future the strategic compass exercises will continue and give a sign of the operational will of Art. 42, par. 7

TEU as an important tool of the CSDP and at the service of integration between EU Member States.

Budget of the EU and related financial support

Art. 41 TEU laid the foundation for the financing of the CSDP under an avenue that distinguishes between non-military and military expenditure. The military expenses borne according to the budget of the EU and the administrative expenses that the institutions incur for the implementation of the CSDP as operational expenses that do not have a military value as for example in peacekeeping and civilian missions. Expenses relating to military operations are borne by the states to defence, except that the Council, unanimously, may decide differently. If the expenses remain borne by the Member States, the distribution is based on the gross national product unless the Council unanimously decides to follow another criterion. The allocation, the contributions paid by the Member States contribute to an initial fund and cover the expenses that are necessary for operations in the military and defense sector. Art. 41 TEU allows the Council the task of adopting the relevant necessary decisions by a qualified majority following a proposal from the High Representative and establishing an initial fund by defining the management methods and establishing the forms of financial control.

In 2021, the European Peace Facility³⁹ was established which aims to strengthen the capacities of third states and regional and international organizations in the military and defense sector as well as the military aspects of such operations as peace support and related conduct. This is a relevant financial base which is part of the security component sector and which manages the common costs of peacekeeping and military missions which strengthens the partners' ability to prevent and deal with crisis situations, thus allowing for a reaction in sectors that present urgent threats to their security in the European context. In Ukraine the Peace Instrument used with the obligation to provide financial resources intended for crises on the European continent in the Middle East and Africa⁴⁰.

This is also foreseen for the defense component which foresees that the costs are borne first of all by the Member States. A part of the administration costs of the EDA are subject to financing rules and are borne by twenty-seven Member States of the EU as well as the same for the financing of projects and are borne by the participating states⁴¹. As regards PESCO in particular Art. 8

³⁹Council Decision (CFSP) 2021/509 of 22 March 2021 establishing a European Peace Facility, and repealing Decision (CFSP) 2015/528, in OJEU/2021, 14ss.

⁴⁰Council Decision (CFSP) 2023/510 of 7 March 2023 amending Council Decision (CFSP) 2022/667 on a measure of assistance in the form of a general support program to the African Union under the European Instrument for Peace for the period 2022-2024, 55, and Council Decision (CFSP) 2023/1440 of 10 July 2023 on an assistance measure under the European Peace Facility in support of the Armed Forces of Ghana, 28ss.

⁴¹See Art. 12 and 19 of the Council Decision (EU) 2015/835 of 11 May 2015 on the position to be taken on behalf of the European Union in the EU-EFTA Joint

of Decision 2017/2315 states that:

“(…) the administrative costs are borne by the EU budget, but the other costs are borne by the twenty-six Member States that join it, including those resulting from the over seventy projects launched, the financing of which is provided by the Member States involved from time to time (…)”.

The possibility of receipt of contributions from the EU places the financial burden on Member States. A direction that plays with the European Defense Fund (EDF)⁴² and lays the foundations for co-financing the budget of the EU, defense investment projects that are presented by suitable legal entities and thus promote efficiency, competition and also innovation on the industrial, technological and defense base contributing to the strategic autonomy of the union. The projects include within PESCO and eligible for financing further co-financing where 10% is presented as a bonus from PESCO. Thus EDF also presents itself as an integration tool that lightens the financial burden of the project and provides membership to new partners⁴³. These types of co-financing are part of the budget of the Union, resulting in a mechanism that connects with Europe⁴⁴

Committee on common transit as regards the adoption of a Decision amending the Convention on a common transit procedure, OJ L 132, 29.5.2015, p. 69-77.

⁴²Regulation (EU) 2021/697 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2021 establishing the European Defense Fund and repealing Regulation (EU) 2018/1092, in OJEU L 170/2021, 149ss.

⁴³The figures for 2022 were for the financing of 41 projects and a financial commitment from the EU budget of over 830 million euros. For 2023, it has increased by 200 million euros as the maximum that has been given to date for the number of projects.

⁴⁴Regulation (EU) 2021/1153 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 7 July 2021 establishing the Connecting Europe Facility and repealing Regulations (EU) No. 1316/2013 and (EU) n. 283/2014, in OJEU L 249/2021, 38ss.

and which finances integration in the field of defense with military mobility.

These are funds that derive within the scope of competences in the fields of industry and research for the EDF, transport, energy for the Connecting Europe Facility. Within this context, the relevant Directive 2019/2235⁴⁵ which provided for exemption from VAT and excise duty for the supply of goods and services as well as imports which directly concern the activities of national armed forces in the context of the defense of the EU⁴⁶.

Competences and interferences that reflect on powers that attribute powers to the European Parliament and the Commission in the context of CSDP/CSDP, weakening them according to the Treaty of Lisbon and act within their full competences. The adoption and management of financial funds on the one hand the parliament as co-decision maker and the commission as the main proponent and manager affects the sector of development and integration of the defense component of the CSDP. It presents itself as a management role that is exercised by the commission and that selectively distributes to

⁴⁵Council Directive (EU) 2019/2235 of 16 December 2019 amending Directive 2006/112/EC on the common system of value added tax and Directive 2008/118/EC concerning the general arrangements for excise duty as regards defence efforts within the Union framework, ST/14126/2019/INIT, OJ L 336, 30.12.2019, p. 10-13.

⁴⁶See, recital 8 of Council Directive (EU) 2019/2235 of 16 December 2019 amending Directive 2006/112/EC on the common system of value added tax and Directive 2008/118/EC on the general system of excise duties as regards defense efforts within the Union, in OJEU L 336/2019, 10ss.

the resources the competence that decides on actions that they attribute to their own co-financing⁴⁷.

Reflections on the strategic compass of 2022

The strategic compass as yet another definitive point of European defense integration began after its adoption by the Foreign Affairs Council on 21 March 2022 and by the subsequent European Council on 24 and 25 March. The objective was to take a decisive, active position in the crisis in Ukraine in a determined way. The replacement of the global strategy of the EU in 2016 surpassed both the contents and the international scenario as well as the progress that occurred within the CSDP⁴⁸.

The Compass reiterated the principles, elements of the past relating to the detection of threats against the security of the Union and the strengthening of the defense as a tool that achieves the relevant deadlines on time (Blockmans, Macchiarini Crosson, Paikin, 2022). La Bussola states that “the objectives envisaged, divided into eighty-one points”, in the areas of “action”, “safety”, “investments” and “partners” objectives that can be remodulated reviewed and updated. In fact, based on the review of the threat analysis expected for 2025 and the objectives achieved, the High Representative will

⁴⁷Art. 11 of Regulation (EU) 2021/697, cit., and art. 21 of Regulation (EU) 2021/1153, cit. Furthermore, see D. Fiott, A. Missiroli, T. Tardy, op. cit., 47ss.

⁴⁸See Document EEAS (2021) 1169 of 8 November 2021.

present proposals for a possible revision of the document. The same High Representative will provide ongoing monitoring, presenting a report annual report on the progress achieved, after consulting the Commission and the EDA.

Already in March 2023, the first Report relating to the implementation of the strategic compass one year after its adoption⁴⁹ underlined that:

“(...) gives an account of the results obtained and in the implementation phase, but, perhaps also due to its brevity (...) does not report missed deadlines and related critical issues (...) the High Representative believes that (...) over the last twelve months, we have made significant progress and achieved concrete results across all four chapters of the strategic compass. This first progress report demonstrates that we are narrowing the gap between our aspirations and our actions (...) fifty-one were to be implemented by 2022. Instead, around twenty-five points were implemented, while for the remaining objectives an extension was imposed of the implementation phase (...) the “action” area provides for the strengthening of the “security” component, in order to make the EU more effective in preventing conflicts and addressing them (...) one of the objectives set concerns, the implementation of Art. 44 TEU by 2023, so as to allow the implementation of peacekeeping missions by a group of capable and willing Member States (...) following Member States' agreement on practical modalities on the Article 44 TEU, we are now in a position to enable a group of willing and able Member States to plan and conduct a mission or operation within the EU framework and thus provide greater flexibility and swiftness in our decision-making (...)”⁵⁰.

An integrative, harmonizing development that activated Art. 44 TEU thus carrying out faster interventions in crisis areas.

Within this context, the European Parliament also invited the

⁴⁹See the Annual Progress Report on the Implementation of the Strategic Compass for Security and Defence, Report of the High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy to the Council, March 2023.

⁵⁰See the Annual Progress Report on the Implementation of the Strategic Compass for Security and Defence, Report of the High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy to the Council, op. cit.

Member States through the Resolution of 18 April 2023 to:

“(…) act on the basis of Art. 44 TEU upon unanimous decision of the Council, which can be achieved through the use of constructive abstention, and urged them to use qualified majority voting for their subsequent decisions⁵¹ (…)

the objective, formulated in the strategic compass, of making the more flexible decision-making process of the CSDP through greater use of constructive abstention pursuant to Art. 31, par. 1, TEU, and the invitation to the Council, already formulated by the Commission in 2018⁵², to take decisions by a qualified majority, when permitted, is also renewed (…).”

This is a flexibility mechanism aimed at allowing adoption (also) in the context CSDP unanimous decisions in the face of non-unanimous consensus among the Member States⁵³. In case of abstention from the vote, each member of the Council can justify its abstention with a formal declaration. It is not obliged to apply the decision, but accepts that it binds the Union. In a spirit of mutual solidarity, the Member State concerned shall abstain from actions that may counteract or impede Union action based on that decision, and the other Member States shall respect its position. This is not adopted if abstention constructive is declared by at least one third of the Member States, comprising at least one third of the EU population. However, it is known that in the CSDP/CSDP area the Council adopts the acts by consensus, therefore there is no voting, so the question arises whether this flexibility mechanism, until now

⁵¹See the Resolution of 19 April 2023 on EU rapid deployment capability, EU battlegroups and Article 44 TEU: prospects for the future (2022/2145(INI)), par. 19.

⁵²Communication from the Commission to the European Council, the European Parliament and the Council, A stronger global role: more efficient decision-making for the EU's common foreign and security policy, COM/2018/647 final, 12 September 2018.

⁵³See Art. 42, par. 4, TEU and art. 46, parr. 2 to 5, TEU.

occasionally used⁵⁴ will be reactivated. The consensus practice appears difficult to be overcome, as demonstrated by the Commission's unsuccessful attempt in 2018 to urge greater use of the qualified majority.

The Report did not report constructive abstention and induced the desire to achieve this improvement in the functioning of the CSDP, thus realizing the action area and giving greater use to the European Peace Instrument and the part relating to the support and strengthening of military capabilities and defense of third states and regional and international organizations. Already since March 2022 this type of financial instrument has been used by imposing a financial increase of three and a half billion euros as requested by the European Council on 29 and 30 June 2023⁵⁵.

The action area operationalizes the mutual assistance clause of a defensive nature as well as the solidarity clause of ex Art. 222 TFEU. The different positions taken by the Member States according to Art. 42, par. 7 TEU and the necessary exercises,

⁵⁴Council doc. CM 448/08, 4 February 2008: "(...) Cyprus recognises the European Union's responsibility to contribute to and, to the extent possible, ensure the stability of the Western Balkans. Cyprus also respects the wish of its partners for an active engagement of the European Union in Kosovo (...) Notwithstanding its firm views, especially on the question of the legal basis for the involvement of the European Union in Kosovo, and any possible future implications in terms of international law, Cyprus has decided not to hinder the decision of the Council to adopt the Joint Action on the EU Rule of Law Mission in Kosovo. In a constructive spirit of loyalty and mutual solidarity, the government of Cyprus has arrived at the above decision which is without prejudice to any future decisions on EU action in similar matters and without prejudice to the status of Kosovo (...)"

⁵⁵The conclusions of the European Council of 29 and 30 June 2023, par. 27.

implemented in the mutual defensive assistance clause, fully and operationally follow European defense policy. At the same time, military mobility is respected which confirms the need to implement this type of PESCO project which highlights the need to effectively move military vehicles and resources within the EU and towards its borders. The report confirmed the operational activities of the project for the implementation which the strategic compass stated that:

“(…) by 2025 we will complete the improvement and harmonization of cross-border procedures (…)”.

The objective was the creation of a rapid reaction force where the strategic compass was created as an evolution of the battlegroup, as a military formation that reduces the strength of military men and disposition of the EU despite the fact that it has never been used. The use of an intervention force as a reserve force guarantees the exit from a scenario of continuous political and military crisis where the rapid reaction force will have a defensive character as an intervention in crisis areas requiring military intervention and the medium-high intensity. The objective is an achievement that awaits the complexities of a multinational composition and the articulation of the establishment of management methods and the activation of a stable base in Brussels. Thus in the security area this strategic compass will have a miscellaneous basis that establishes and implements the measures that enable the EU to trace threats of

different types including hybrid ones. Cyber defense and cybersecurity between 2023 and 2024 develops the capacity to guarantee that there is a registration required by the report in the creation of a hybrid toolbox that uses hybrid threats and the preparation of activities necessary for guaranteeing access and presence in the Union of non-terrestrial domains.

In the investment area, two financial aspects can be noted. On the one hand we have military spending which increases investments in the military sector and decreases financial fragmentation in it. Thus, cooperation in development and capacity is intensified by PESCO, through the monitoring of twenty-six Member States where by 2025 -with financial constraints that are assumed- are part of an entry of a cooperation force. This reduces financial fragmentation which provides for a boost to the carrying out of procurement in the defense sector by 2023 thanks to the active contribution of the Commission to the related aspects in the TFEU context⁵⁶.

The report notes a relative increase in military spending that is not uniform across Member States and breaks the context of the CSDP. Financial fragmentation characterizes military procurement at a level of cooperation between Member States,

⁵⁶See the communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, Contribution of the Commission to European Defence, 15 February 2022, COM/2022/60 final, in particular 18. See also the Annual Progress Report, op. cit., par. 15.

improving that the value of purchases is too low and leads the High Representative to note that “we are mobilizing EU tools to spend better together”.

As regards the partner area, the development of relations with the EU and its partners as well as the relevant issues relating to security are dealt with jointly. The multilateral partners and the EU strengthen through the partnership with the UN and NATO, the African Union and the ASEAN a consolidation of active collaborations as can also be seen through the NATO joint declaration of January 2023. The cooperative dialogue, the bilateral partnerships on measure and the strategic compass places the individual third states that are geographically close to the EU at a more qualifyable stage. These are the countries involved with PESCO as well as in the Western Balkan region, the Near East and South and the Indo-Pacific region as well as Latin America.

The Strategic Compass has an important path where the objectives are lower and which respect in a pre-established way the implementation of the prospects that are achieved in the medium-long term. The interventions of the developments are sudden and it is difficult to extend the relative times for a gradual definition of a common defense policy.

Implementation prospects through Art. 42, par. 2, TEU

From the path we have taken so far we understand that the defense policy has not yet been concluded as expected but not even implemented. Integration in the sector has not reached such a high level of cooperation as necessary. A level that puts this type of policy into the definition with the particular elements that characterize it and that include it, thus obtaining the elements of thought of the Commission that have been designed since 2017 for a cooperation that will be concluded by 2025.

Elements that conclude in the following:

“(...) voluntary and non-binding cooperation (a) cooperation as a rule (b) and, finally, the development of a common defense (c). According to the Commission, in scenario (b) cooperation between Member States becomes the rule, therefore they intensify the alignment of defense planning and acquisitions of military assets and the maintenance of capabilities takes place in a shared manner (...) the national armed forces they acquire greater interoperability and duplications are reduced. In this scenario, the Member States coordinated in this way could benefit from financial contributions from the EU budget, in order to develop, at a multinational level, the necessary defense capabilities (...)”.

These are elements of a scenario that is not yet concluded given that the defense integration stage is linked to scenarios a) and b) and goes beyond voluntary cooperation to a framework of a common defense policy. Cooperation as a rule demonstrates that PESCO in the legal framework binds in an inclusive way the affirmation of defensive but not exceptional and not perfectly organized cooperation. The strategic compass is oriented towards cooperation that follows the path of rules in litteram. The objectives and contents called the characteristics of the

defense policy that come from the pre-established elements of the Commission that date back to 2017 especially with regard to the financial aspects and cooperation between Member States as a stable, precise regulation⁵⁷. The development of defense policy has shown that the strategic compass can achieve some stages and elements by 2030 as definitions of a common defense policy in the EU. There are many variables with deadlines that will be posted in times that have not been reached.

The second objective of Art. 42, par. 2, TEU worries us since the EU does not have a common defense policy. The consideration of the absence of a definition of common defense and the identification of the Member States formulates the ideal hypotheses of a common defense which leads to the creation of a European army where the EU avails itself in case of necessity of an effective number greater than the current one extension of the Union⁵⁸. Thus the benefits will be a replacement of twenty-seven national armed forces with a common defense leading to flourishing economies and operational advantages.

⁵⁷Annual Progress Report, op. cit., par. 5: “(...) the start of the war against Ukraine, EU Member States have announced increases in defence spending (...). We need to seize this once-in-a-generation opportunity to fix the errors of the past and progress towards stronger collaboration, designing and acquiring next-generation capabilities together. Spending together must become the norm instead of the exception (...)”.

⁵⁸It is considered that the army planned for a European defense community was started in the 1950s during the Europe of 6 and approximately 500,000 soldiers were expected. Now in the Europe of 27 member states the numbers are certainly higher. We are talking about an army figure ranging from 2,000,000 and at the same time NATO includes a figure of around 2,100,000 personnel.

Concluding remarks

European defense should be approached as a calming force for maintaining peace, security and the protection of human rights within the principle of subsidiarity. Common defense is inspired by an American-style army model as a federal component with responsibility for territorial areas, thus following a dual model that constitutes the old fundamentalist dream of a small European army for the maintenance of a national guard by the Member States of the Union.

The forms of defense cooperation open the way for an active reorganization which makes it necessary to define a common defense policy in the indispensable creation of duplications and dispersions. The different forms of cooperation (such as the various military groupings) within the scope of the CSDP⁵⁹ absorb the common defense and make us think of conduct inspired by PESCO and EDA. Relations with third states will be regulated by forms that follow the paths of affiliation to the CSDP and followed in relation to specific aspects of security and defense.

Obviously the same rules do not apply to NATO. The common defense policy and common defense do not go beyond the lines of maintaining the structure of relations with the EU and the alliance where currently the concepts of complementarity and

⁵⁹Art. 42, par. 2 and 3, TEU.

interoperability between the CSDP and transatlantic defense continue to play an important and primacy role in defense in the European context also when the Union can have its own common defense in terms of future complementarity and interoperability of two two-speed defenses where the advantages of this type of scenario lead to a European collective defense. A defense that within the European context should take a position for the maintenance of peace, global security, European stability and the protection of human lives. A difficult but not unattainable path.

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